

Terms of Reference for the working group *'Financial plan for FAIR data'* in connection with the National Strategy for Data Management based on the FAIR principles.

Mandated period: 2023-2024

Preamble

The working group is established based on the 'Remit and Terms of Reference for the Reference group for the implementation of the National Strategy for Data Management Based on the FAIR Principles'. The working group focuses on the areas described below. In addition, the working group should observe the implementation of the national strategy by universities and other relevant research institutions, and through coordination of activities across institutions, support the implementation of the strategy. Coordination can for example, take place through workshops, seminars, and the establishment of a common document archive where 'best practices' are documented. It is not the task of the working group to engage in the implementation or management of projects or sub-projects at individual institutions.

The working group reports on its activities to the FAIR Reference group - typically concrete and targeted activities that support the institutions' own implementations. The FAIR Reference group reports the universities' progress to The Ministry of Higher Education and Science. The institutions themselves choose the order, process, schedule, etc. in relation to the specific implementation of the National Strategy for Data Management Based on the FAIR Principles.

Background for the Terms of Reference

In Denmark the Ministry of Higher Education and Science published a strategy for national collaboration on digital research infrastructure in 2018, recommending the development of a strategy for data management based on the FAIR principles (hereinafter referred to as 'the strategy'). This strategy was published on September 1st, 2021.

The purpose of the strategy is to establish a basis for decisions on a national implementation and funding of data management practice based on the FAIR principles (**F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable, **R**eusable). This means that data should be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, and the conditions for the use and reuse of data should be clearly formulated. The aim is to significantly increase the amount of research data in Denmark that adheres to the FAIR principles, so Denmark can be a proactive participant in the European development towards better utilization of the value of research data.

The Terms of Reference is part of the implementation plan that the established Reference Group (FAIR Reference Group) for the strategy has been tasked with developing, and describes how the work on the sub-elements, which the working group is appointed to address, is organized.

Purpose of the working group

The strategy contains a range of principles and proposed focus areas to support the implementation of the principles. Some of the focus areas should be addressed by the stakeholders themselves, and some of the implementation will be carried out by DeiC (Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium). However, some of the implementation requires national coordination across stakeholders (e.g. research institutions, DeiC) and this is the part of the implementation that the working group should assist in developing and observing.

The working group should propose actions that address efforts requiring special national coordination for the following focus areas of the strategy:

7. *EU programs (e.g., Horizon Europe) require grant recipients to develop data management plans in connection with grant applications. To what extent can national research funding organizations benefit from following this practice?*
8. *Can the research data that is the basis for published research results, be required to be made available according to FAIR principles after the project's completion, at a minimum with metadata and a persistent identifier (PID), even when the data is not openly accessible?*
9. *What costs related to data management can be included in budgets?*

The working group should continuously observe developments in the mentioned areas through contact with research institutions. This can be done through meetings with relevant stakeholders, conducting small workshops, and small surveys that show the institutions' status regarding policies and support for FAIR. The work should be coordinated with already existing stakeholder groups, e.g. DeiC DM-Forum, and the Universities' CiO forum among others.

Working methods, composition, and deliverables of the working group

The working group is one of six working groups that collectively follows the national development of the strategy's focus areas and report to the FAIR Reference group. Initially, the observations and recommendations of the working groups are included in the preparation of an action plan for the implementation of the strategy. The action plan must be submitted to the Ministry of Higher Education and Science by March 1st, 2024. Based on the work of the working groups, the FAIR Reference group must prepare a report describing progress in the strategy. This report must be submitted to the Ministry of Higher Education and Science by the end of 2024. Therefore, the working group is expected to meet the following deliverables:

- A. Deliverable by March 1st, 2024: Action plan for work until the end of 2024, which includes:
 1. Benchmarks for relevant efforts
 2. Proposals for cross-cutting coordinating national activities, such as workshops, seminars, and knowledge exchange

- B. Deliverable by mid-2024, in connection with a status meeting with the FAIR Reference group:
1. Account of collected data for the benchmarks mentioned under A
 2. Status of contact with universities and other relevant institutions
- C. Deliverable by the end of 2024 to the FAIR Reference group:
1. Contribution to reporting according to the action plan.

Composition of the working group

- Universities
- Ministry of Higher Education and Science
- Sector research institutions
- The Royal Library
- University libraries
- The National Archives
- DeiC

Organization

The FAIR Reference group appoints a chairperson from among the members of the working group. The chairperson, in collaboration with the DeiC secretariat leads the work and is the contact person to the FAIR Reference group.

Meeting cadence

The working group decides its own meeting format and frequency.

Resources and finance

DeiC will provide secretariat support to the FAIR Reference group and working groups, and DeiC will also cover expenses for seminars, workshops etc.